

Harmony of social and moral values in the development of countries

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Abstract

In the article, it is analyzed that education cannot be implemented without education, and education without education, that these two concepts are considered the main axis roots of enlightenment, that education is of high quality only where there is education, and that education is important not only in education, but in the processes taking place in the whole society.

Key words: upbringing, education, enlightenment, youth, changes, future.

INTRODUCTION

One of the gratifying things is that in recent years, in our country, as in Japan, attention has been paid to science and education, especially to the education of young people. In this, equal attention is paid to continuous education at all levels. For this purpose, the "MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN" was established for the first time in the history of our country. The purpose of this ministry is to spread enlightenment to our children from their early years. In the system of public education, which is the longest-lasting and most important stage of imparting

enlightenment to our youth, fundamental changes are being given great attention and fundamental changes are being implemented in the school education system.

MAIN PART

Considerable work has been done to improve the material and technical conditions of schools, to raise the status of teachers, and it is planned to continue in the future. Higher education, which is considered the highest level of education, is experiencing positive changes no less than other areas. Many measures have been developed to train qualified specialists with modern knowledge, and the processes of ensuring their implementation are being continued. There is no doubt that all these reforms will ultimately serve to bring social relations to a new level in our country.

We have used the words education together in many cases in our thoughts above. The reason for this is that education cannot be carried out without education, and education cannot be carried out without education. Both of these concepts are the main axis roots of enlightenment. Education will be of quality only where there is education¹. Education is important not only in education, but also in the processes taking place in society as a whole. French scientist Lametrie said that "without education, there would be very few good people in the world. Only education improves the inner world of a person. "Only education can direct a person to be useful for the benefit of other people." In fact, education is a social force that determines the direction of social relations. It is known that the subject

¹ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

of social relations is a person². How a person behaves depends on his upbringing. Simply put, people interact when they live in society. This relationship can be good or bad. Or else it can be a mixture of good and bad. It is also possible for everyone to act in their own interest, without doing good or bad to each other. There is a proverb in our people: "If you can't do good, then don't do bad." In a sense, this is also a kind of upbringing. But the beauty of the society is that the people who live in it do good to each other, use each other and make a living taking into account each other's interests. Of course, this is based on education. Because only a well-educated person can do good to other people and they can sympathize with the pain and worries of others. A large number of people who have received such education will lead to the further development of that society³. Humanity, humaneness, and generosity are necessary for all members of the society. However, it is especially important for the representatives of the materially rich stratum of the society, that is, for the rich. Why is it said, "The duty of a rich man is to care for the happiness of the society and light up the hearts of others with his happiness" should be. We agree with this opinion that poor, poor or middle-class people who don't have much wealth can't lend a helping hand to others even if they want to. Because their financial capabilities don't allow it. It's true that most of this category of people were brought up, good people. We don't mean to disparage them. But that's the truth.

It must be admitted that most of our compatriots are in this situation now. If

² Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). ЖАМИЯТНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВИДА БОШҚАРУВ ВА ТАРБИЯ САНЪАТИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 359-365.

³ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Одилбек Дониёр Ўғли Бозорбоев, Хусниддин Равшанбек Раджапбаев (2022). ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШГА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 286-291.

they were rich and had surplus funds, they would help those in need. We can give dozens, hundreds and thousands of life examples with similar content. One conclusion can be drawn from them, which is that if rich and self-satisfied people in society are kind and generous to those around them, if they can share their happiness with others, then cooperation and harmony will be established there⁴. Also, conflicts and conflicts of a social nature are not allowed to arise. These situations primarily serve the interests of the rich. After all, in a stable society where peace prevails, the wealth of the rich continues to grow. God forbid, if there is instability and a turbulent situation, the rich will suffer the most. Because at their disposal there are different levels of trade points, production enterprises and other economic objects. Their activities are in crisis by themselves. This means that income stops and losses begin. Then there will be no people in a disorderly society. Instead, a crowd appears. And it is known where the crowd will attack and close in the first place. It's up to us to make sure things don't go in such an unpleasant direction. We should not only think about our own interests, but also consider the interests of the society and serve for its development. "If we bring happiness to society, we create our own happiness together with it"⁵. A very valid point.

CONCLUSION

After all, society is made up not of one person, but of millions, or even billions of people (in the case of China and India). It is the intelligence, dreams, aspirations, human or inhuman behavior of these people that determine the future

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Одилбек Дониёр Ўғли Бозорбоев, Хусниддин Равшанбек Раджапбаев (2022). ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОИЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШГА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 286-291.

⁵ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). ЖАМИЯТНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВИДА БОШҚАРУВ ВА ТАРБИЯ САНЪАТИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 359-365.

of the society. We didn't use the phrase inhuman behavior for nothing. Because, no matter how nice it is, the existence of a perfect, ideal society is very doubtful. No society can be made up of 100 percent perfect people in real life. Like it or not, there are different people in any society. In particular, there are bad guys and villains who hold back the development of society. Society has created laws to restrain such people and fights against them through these laws. No matter how hard it is, we have to admit that "Only the fear of the law stops evil people."

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